

DIGITAL PRESERVATION POLICIES: A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF PORTUGAL AND SPAIN

Catarina Gasche

*Universidade de Lisboa
Faculdade de Letras
Centro de Estudos Clássicos
Portugal
catarinagasche@edu.ulisboa
a.pt
<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-7655-7473>*

Luís Corujo

*Universidade de Lisboa
Faculdade de Letras
Centro de Estudos Clássicos
Portugal
luiscorujo@edu.ulisboa.pt
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4411-2453>*

Abstract – In a world where information is predominantly digital, digital preservation has become a critical concern for both nations and organizations. This paper aims to assess the state of digital preservation in Portugal and Spain, two neighboring countries that frequently collaborate on digital transition initiatives. To address this question, we conducted a literature review to examine digital preservation policies, their characteristics, and their significance within organizations, complemented by an analysis of the legislation and policies in each country.

Digital preservation in Portugal and Spain exhibits significant disparities between the two countries. On the one hand, Spain has enacted multiple legislative measures that clarify and prioritize this issue within its governmental framework. On the other hand, Portugal's legislation remains outdated, and the government has demonstrated reluctance to pass new laws addressing digital preservation since 2018. Despite the inevitability of digital transformation, information preservation is often treated as a secondary concern.

Submission Type – Full Paper

Keywords – Digital Preservation; Policy; Portugal; Spain

Conference Topics – Haerenga – Journey

I. INTRODUCTION

As modern society generates and manages vast amounts of digital information, digital preservation has emerged as a critical concern. Across the globe, countries and organizations have established digital preservation policies to outline the necessary processes for ensuring that digital information does not become lost over time. This study aims to analyze the digital preservation policies in Portugal and Spain, given their geographical proximity and governmental cooperation in facilitating digital transition initiatives.

This paper begins with a literature review on digital preservation, emphasizing the importance of policies and identifying the key characteristics that define an effective digital preservation policy. Building on this foundation, we then examine the official documents and legislation related to digital preservation in Portugal and Spain.

II. METHODS

This research employed document analysis to collect and examine various data sources. The paper is structured into two main sections: a literature review, which provides an overview of the current

state of knowledge on digital preservation, and an analysis of the legislation and policies in Portugal and Spain.

For the literature review we conducted a search on Web of Science and Scopus for articles published in the last five years using the key terms: "polic*" AND "preservation" AND "digital", restricted to the fields of social sciences, information science and computer science. The initial search yielded 294, which, after the removal of duplicates, resulted in a final selection of 247 articles. Through the analysis of the abstracts and conclusions and due to space limitations of 247 only 2 articles were deemed relevant for inclusion to the study, as they referred to national digital preservation policies. Additionally, to complement the review, we consulted foundational literature, including documents from various organizations that have researched or established digital preservation frameworks.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

The advent of information technologies and the growing reliance of organizations on electronically created and maintained information have intensified global concerns regarding the preservation of digital records [1].

Digital preservation encompasses a wide range of definitions. In Ferreira [2, p.20] it's described as "a set of activities or processes responsible for ensuring continued long-term access to information and other cultural heritage existing in digital formats (...) consists of the ability to ensure that digital information remains accessible and with sufficient authenticity qualities so that it can be interpreted in the future using a technological platform different from that used at the time of its creation". Similarly, in [3, p.18] INTERPARES defines it as "The specific process of maintaining digital materials during and across different generations of technology over time, irrespective where they reside".

A. Levels of the digital preservation application

Digital preservation is structured at multiple levels, beginning with the formulation of a digital preservation policy. This policy is described as "high-level document produced at the institutional level that specifies the strategies and constraints at the general level. The policy is abstract and is useful for setting the framework for digital preservation

actions in custodial institutions but does not enter concrete preservation planning or actions" [4, p.92]. While some authors advocate for a dual-level framework consisting of policy and strategy [5], others propose a more comprehensive three-tier approach, which includes policy, planning, and program [4].

Table 1 – Different approaches for the levels of digital preservation

Dual level	Three-tiered
Digital preservation policy: "defines the rationale for undertaking digital preservation, elucidating its alignment with organizational objectives, its role in achieving strategic goals, and the risks of non-compliance. Secondly, it establishes authoritative guidelines for the entire preservation process, articulating roles and responsibilities, defining success criteria, and setting standards for appraisal and adherence"	Digital preservation policy: high level-document that points the strategies for digital preservation. It is abstract and sets the frameworks for the processes developed to achieve preservation
Digital preservation strategy: "broad approach adopted by an organisation to ensure that the content of digital records remains in a usable form over time. The strategy works by identifying specific triggers which will determine when digital preservation activities may take place"	Digital preservation plan: "is more concrete (it can be general-strategic or specific-operational) and includes the specification of actions to manage digital preservation at the institutional level and to implement the policy for a given purpose, as well as its proposed implementation and traceability"
	Digital preservation strategy: "organized, coherent and integrated set of digital preservation processes and procedures that are related to each other and are developed simultaneously or successively, with the necessary resources and with the aim of achieving digital continuity, all of this framed within the preservation plan and the preservation policy"

Sources: [4], [5]

B. The importance of digital preservation

The significance of such a policy is emphasized as the cornerstone of a digital preservation program. In [6, p.3] ERPA states that "from an external point of view, a written policy is a sign that the organization takes the responsibility to preserve digital material".

In contrast, the absence of such a policy may indicate a lack of organizational commitment [7].

The importance of formalizing digital preservation strategies within institutional frameworks to underscore the long-term sustainability of digital resources. In this context, a written policy serves as an external indicator of responsibility and organizational intent [7].

C. Structural Aspects and Relationships

Delos describes [8, p.44] the policy domain as “the set of conditions, rules, terms or regulations governing the operation”. It categorizes policies based on characteristics such as compliance, context, expression, and application, and also by scope, which includes system, content, functionality, and user policies. These policies are influenced by various quality parameters and regulatory resources and are embedded in information objects.

Digital preservation policies must align with complementary documentation, including national and international standards, legislation, and frameworks for system development. Furthermore, policies can be integrated with related fields, such as records management and digital preservation policies [5]. This comprehensive approach ensures that policies are consistent and effective in supporting digital preservation efforts.

D. Types of digital preservation policies

Digital preservation policies can take various forms, including national and institutional approaches. For example, Norway's National Strategy for Digital Preservation and Dissemination of Cultural Heritage [9] and the policies of the National Library of Australia [10] or Library and Archives Canada [11] exemplify national and institutional-level efforts to safeguard digital content. These policies provide clear frameworks for preserving digital assets, ensuring their long-term accessibility and usability. Furthermore, such policies are not standalone but are embedded in broader strategic and legislative contexts, which often involve cross-disciplinary collaboration, including archives, libraries, and museums.

E. Analysis of Existing Policies

The study by Sheldon [12] analyzed 33 digital preservation policies and identified 19 key topics that were commonly addressed across them. These topics include: Access and Use, Preservation

Model/Strategy, Accessioning and Ingest, Preservation Planning, Audit, Rights and Restriction Management, Bibliography, Roles and Responsibilities, Collaboration, Security Management, Content Scope, Selection/Appraisal, Glossary/Terminology, Staff Training/Education, Mandates, Storage, Duplication and Backup, Metadata or Documentation, Sustainability Planning, and Policy/Strategy Review. These topics reflect the broad range of concerns that digital preservation policies address, from access and use to long-term sustainability planning, ensuring that digital content remains accessible and usable over time.

The study by Souza & Aganette [13] conducted an analysis of six key documents to delineate the stages of policy development and their structural elements. These documents include a range of authors and organizations: [14], [15], [16], [6], [17], [18]. The authors emphasized critical aspects such as defining objectives, conducting contextual analysis, planning for implementation, and outlining responsibilities [13, pp. 91-95].

The six documents presented the following guidelines for the development of digital preservation policies: definition of objectives; institution/organisation of the working group; review of regulations and good practices; contextual analysis (administrative structure, human resources and institutional support, existing gaps and weaknesses, document management policies, documents that are covered); policy review with stakeholders; approval of the policy by senior management; definition of the implementation plan.

Through the analysis of 6 documents, the authors were also able to obtain a model structure that outlines the structure of a digital preservation policy, as seen in Table 2.

Table 2 - Different parts of the structure of digital preservation policy

principles and objectives: “motivation for the development of the digital preservation policy (...) ii. the guiding principles through which digital preservation will be developed (...) aligning goals and objectives of the institution and the digital preservation policy: reliability, authenticity, fixity (...) iv. the institution's purposes in developing digital preservation (...) v. the institution's commitment to digital preservation (...) vi. the importance of digital preservation for the institution (...) vii. information about the digital document production process”

references and related sources : “documents used in the development of the policy (...) ii. international and national norms, standards and guidelines (...) iii. institutional regulations related to the digital preservation policy (...) iv. good practices and policies of other organizations used (...) v. establish compliance of the policy with the OAIS Model”
glossary and definitions
Scope
access and use
responsibilities : stakeholders, informations about audits and certifications)
declare the technological resources assumed for the development of preservation: “describe security and preservation systems used: reliable digital repositories (...) ii. policies for standardizing formats, monitoring and converting files (...) iii. strategies that are appropriate to the level and type of digital preservation adopted by the institution”
risks
financial resources
cooperation with partners
implementation guidance
digital preservation policy revisions and version control: “responsible party and date of update; ii. responsible party, date and information about the audit and evaluation of the implementation of the policy; iii. time interval between reviews;iv. date of the last review of the policy; v. date of the next review or effective date of the policy; vi. version number of the policy; vii. if the policy has been replaced, the date on which the replacement occurred; viii. each policy should refer to the policies it replaces (or, if it has been replaced, refer to the updated version)”
mandate

Source: [13, pp. 93-95]

F. Recommendations for Effective Policies

The study by APARSEN [19, pp.31-33] presented key recommendations for the development of effective digital preservation policies, underscoring the importance of financial sustainability, integration with core business functions, collaboration with stakeholders, public accessibility, and explicit mechanisms for periodic updates. Furthermore, the recommendations stress the inclusion of risk assessments, the specification of relevant standards and interoperability, the clear delegation of

responsibilities, and the establishment of transparent licensing processes.

IV. RESULTS

A. Spain

In Spain, archives fall under the jurisdiction of the Ministry of Culture. Upon consulting the Ministry's website, particularly the archives section, it is possible to access a dedicated area for professional resources [20]. These resources include applicable legislation such as the Código de Derecho Cultural (Cultural Rights Code) [21] and the Código de Archivos y Patrimonio Documental (Archives and Documentary Heritage Code) [22]. Additionally, the Subdirección General de los Archivos Estatales, which is responsible for state archives and operates within the Ministry, publishes a series of draft documents addressing electronic administration and digital transformation for the general administration of the State. This collection of guides covers topics such as the transfer and entry of electronic documents and files into the single electronic archive, data governance, digital preservation, assessment and disposal of electronic documents, and the intersection of artificial intelligence and e-government, along with its archival impact. The only guide published to date is El archivo electrónico único (The Unique Electronic Archive), released in March 2025 [23].

These three documents were consulted to understand the context of digital preservation in Spain. The following table presents the relevant laws and articles highlighted in these documents concerning digital preservation.

Table 3 – Spanish legislation related to digital preservation

Cultural Rights Code	Archives and Documentary Heritage Code	The Unique Electronic Archive
Articles 21° and 22° chapter VI governed by the Royal Decree 1708/2011, of 18 of november,	Articles 21° and 22° chapter VI archives it is governed by the Royal Decree 1708/2011	Article 54 Royal Decree 203/2021, of 30 march
Law 11/2007, of 22 of june	Article 5 of Royal Decree 1517/2009, of 2 of october	Royal Decree 1708/2011
	Article 2 and 50 Law 6/2022, of 5 august	Royal Decree 203/2021 (article 55) in development of article 17 of the Law 39/2015

Cultural Rights Code	Archives and Documentary Heritage Code	The Unique Electronic Archive
	Royal Decree 2023 (article 54) in accordance with article 46 of the Law 40/2015, and article 27 of the Law 39/2015	

Sources: [21], [22], [23]

The Cultural Rights Code (last updated in November 2024) in chapter VI section 4 electronic documents and digital preservation, article 20 says that all ministerial departments and related public law entities must adopt organizational decisions and necessary technical measures to ensure the recovery and conservation of electronic documents throughout their life cycle [21, p.393]. These measures include: “clear identification by an unique code; minimum mandatory metadata; inclusion of an electronic index in the case of the electronic files that is recoverable; complete and immediate retrieval of documents by online consultation; the adoption of measures to ensure the preservation of the memory of the legal entities that had influence over the documents to better understand the context of their production; maintenance of the probative value of documents and files; the transfer of electronic files to the historical archives for the preservation ensuring medium and long term preservation; when eliminating information and in need of eliminating the physical version it has to be done as procedure and accompanied by a record of the process; includes the evaluation and establishment of strategies for preservation such as emulation, migration and conversion of formats” [21, pp. 393-394].

Article 21 of the same law refers to the promotion of information technologies in information management, enabling ministerial departments and their subordinate entities to preserve, manage, and access information. The use of these management systems is aligned with Law 11/2007 [24]. This article also specifies the development of digital repositories that define formats for the exchange of information via metadata and classification by various administrative bodies. These digital archives must meet minimum requirements for protection, access, integrity, availability, authenticity, confidentiality, traceability, and conservation of information. Furthermore, the development and implementation of Integrated Information and Archive Management

Systems must occur on shared computer platforms for updates and access via the internet. The implementation of telematic services that facilitate information management and enable responses to citizens' requests is also emphasized [19].

The Archives and Documentary Heritage Code (last updated in March 2025) includes provisions of Royal Decree 1708/2011 [25] and has additional legislation addressing digital preservation including [26], which established the *Board of Trustees of the General Archive of Simancas*. Article 5 of this decree outlines the functions of the governing body of the archive, which is responsible for knowing and reporting on plans and programs for acquisitions, preservation, and digital preservation of documentary collections [26, p.231]. Furthermore Law 6/2022 [27] defines digital preservation and specifies in Article 50 that the formats of electronic documents must adhere to mandatory digital preservation requirements, “when there is a risk of obsolescence of the format or when the format is no longer one of those accepted at any given time by the legislation in force, digital preservation actions shall be applied, such as standardised procedures for authentic copies of documents with a change of format, labelling with information on the format used and, where appropriate, migrations or conversions of formats, both for the electronic transmission of the file and for the reference to it for accessing and downloading it” [27,p.31].

The most recent legislation addressing digital preservation is in Royal Decree 203/2021 [28], specifically Chapter II, Electronic Documents Archive in Article 54, Conservation of Electronic Documents. This article stipulates that public administration bodies and their dependent entities are required to preserve, in electronic form, all documents created during administrative procedures, as well as any documents created for evidentiary purposes, as outlined in Law 40/2015 [29]. To ensure compliance, line 4 specifies “that to ensure the preservation, access and consultation of archived electronic documents regardless of the time elapsed since their issue, the data may be transferred to other formats and supports that guarantee access from different applications, in accordance with the provisions of article 27 of Law 39/2015 [30] and the specific regulations on archives and documentary, historical and cultural heritage. Likewise, digital preservation actions shall be planned to guarantee the long-term conservation of digital documents and thus enable

compliance with the provisions of the previous paragraph” [30, p.45]. Article 27 of Law 39/2015 [30] specifies the validity and effectiveness of copies produced by Public Administrations, in accordance with the *Esquema Nacional de Interoperabilidad* (National Interoperability Scheme) and the *Esquema Nacional de Seguridad* (National Security Scheme), along with their associated technical development regulations.

The draft for the exclusive electronic archive [23], published in March 2025, is grounded in Law 39/2015, which mandates that public administrations maintain and manage a unified electronic archive. This archive must store electronic documents “in a format that guarantees the authenticity, integrity and preservation of the document, as well as its consultation regardless of the time elapsed since its issuance” [30, p.23].

This guide also includes the provisions of Article 54 [28] and Articles 21 and 22 of Chapter VI [25]. As highlighted, “there is no doubt that there are clear references to the preservation of documentation in the single electronic archive throughout the regulations analysed. From the references to the characteristics that document formats must meet to guarantee long-term preservation in [30] (Article 17.2) to the direct references in Article 54 [28], also oriented along the same lines, that is, to the management of document formats (and their versions) (...) Additionally, the draft refers to the preservation measures that must be applied in these terms (Article 54.4)” [23, pp.52-54].

To apply the preservation actions outlined the guide summarises the steps required: the definition of preservation requirements through other action models, such as the forthcoming draft on digital preservation and preservation databases, alongside additional reference models. These reports, combined with feedback from the professional community, establish the minimum requirements, which are then translated into technical standards for interoperability, such as the National Interoperability Scheme.

The final stage involves defining technical standards that “address the conditions and requirements relating to the preservation of electronic documents to ensure their authenticity, integrity, confidentiality, availability and traceability, as well as the protection, recovery and physical and logical preservation of the documents and their context” [23, p.53]. These include the Technical

Interoperability Standard for the preservation of electronic documentation and the Technical Interoperability Standard for the processing and preservation of databases established in the Royal Decree 4/2010 [31]. This draft also emphasizes that digital preservation is guided by the Spatial Data and Information Transfer Systems - Open Archival Information System (OAIS) Reference Model [32], though further discussions on this topic will be addressed in the draft on digital preservation.

B. Portugal

In Portugal, information on digital preservation is scarce, and the existing legislation is outdated, offering only vague references to this area. The most recent government initiative, the National Digital Strategy, was outlined in the *Resolução do Conselho de Ministros* (Resolution of the Council of Ministers), which is a council consisting of the Prime Minister and ministers responsible for key policy debates. Resolution No. 207/2024 [33] defines the action plan for the period 2025-2026, which includes 49 actions grouped into 16 initiatives. Although the document emphasizes the need to position Portugal at the forefront of innovation and digital transformation, particularly in the context of a global digital revolution that is reshaping how we live, work, and interact, it does not mention digital preservation.

Portuguese archival legislation is governed by two key pieces of law: Decree law n.º 447/88 [34], where only specifies the preservation of information as Conservation of audio-visual and machine-readable documentation in Article 2, and Decree law n.º 16/93 [35], which establishes the general regime for archives and archival heritage. However, these laws provide minimal guidance on digital preservation, referring to conservation only as operations that allow the safekeeping, access and use of this heritage, without which it would remain useless. Despite the outdated nature of this legislation, recent regulatory measures, such as the new *Portarias de gestão de documentos* (Regulations for Records Management and Disposition) based on Decree law n.º 447/88 [34], have highlighted the necessity for digital preservation plans to ensure the security, reliability, integrity, authenticity, durability, and accessibility of information and the information systems used by organizations.

In response to this evolving concern, DGLAB (the General Directorate for Book, Archives, and

Libraries) issued two guidelines in 2011 and 2019 to support the development of digital preservation plans, offering technical assistance for their preparation. However, despite these efforts, DGLAB's proposed new Legal Framework for the Classification and Appraisal of Records, which includes provisions for digital preservation, has been awaiting government approval since 2018.

This proposal emphasizes the importance of digital preservation, making it a requirement to guarantee the long-term preservation of both digital and analog media. It also advocates for the application of the OAIS (Open Archival Information System) reference model for digital preservation repositories, which would be subject to audit and certification through the ISO 16363 standard, which deals with the auditing and certification of trustworthy digital repositories [36]. It also points out that the "covered entities must prepare and implement a digital preservation plan (DPP), in accordance with DGLAB guidelines, aimed at ensuring the preservation of archival information with a lifespan of more than 7 years. The DPP must be completed within 3 years after approval of the respective Selection Table, for approval by DGLAB; They must implement, update and review it (every 3 years); The digital preservation plan is implemented through the application of organizational and technological measures indicated in the General Regulations, supplemented with technical guidelines from DGLAB" [37]. And every 2 years a report must be sent to DGLAB to show that "guaranteeing the security, authenticity, integrity, functionality, structure, content and metadata associated with the digital information maintained by the entity" [37], since all the information in the repositories independently of their original have probative value.

V. CONCLUSION

Comprehensive digital preservation policies are essential for ensuring long-term access to digital resources. They offer a strategic framework, define roles and responsibilities, and establish guidelines for maintaining digital integrity. As demonstrated by existing research and best practices, effective policies require a structured approach, integration with organizational objectives, and alignment with international standards to address the complex challenges of digital preservation.

Despite the widespread recognition of the significance of these policies in safeguarding information, several countries remain lagging in this regard. Upon examining various policies and legislative frameworks, it becomes evident that Spain, since 2010, has been progressively passing or updating laws to address digital preservation. By 2025, the Subdirección General de los Archivos Estatales has published several guides, incorporating input from the professional community to discuss the digital transformation of public administration. In contrast, Portugal, although it has developed national digital strategies under successive governments, has overlooked the issue of preservation. The country's policies and legislation are outdated, and the government has repeatedly delayed discussions on the development of new regulations. The comparative analysis of these two countries reveals that, despite the inevitability of digital transformation, the safeguarding of this new form of assets is often perceived as a secondary concern.

The analysis of this topic is still ongoing as this is a more comprehensive investigation, future articles will address aspects such as an assessment of the institutional adoption of these policies in Portuguese and Spanish institutions, allowing us to have a full picture of these policies not only as legislation but also as a praxis in each country.

REFERENCES

- [1] F. BARBEDO, L. CORUJO, e M. SANT'ANA, «Recomendações para a produção de planos de preservação digital», Lisboa: Direção-Geral do Livro, dos Arquivos e das Bibliotecas (DGLAB), 2011.
- [2] M. Ferreira, Introdução à preservação digital: conceitos, estratégias e actuais consensos. Universidade do Minho. Escola de Engenharia (EEng), 2006
- [3] InterPARES, The InterPARES 2 Project Glossary, 2025. Accessed 8 March 2025. [Online]. Available: http://www.interpares.org/ip2/display_file.cfm?doc=ip2_glossary.pdf&CFID=39645427&CFTOKEN=23457456
- [4] A. Sáenz-Giraldo, «La preservación digital sistémica. Propuesta metodológica a partir de la documentación de experiencias en Colombia», ICS, n.º 50, pp. 87-101, jun. 2024.
- [5] National Archives, Digital Preservation Policies: Guidance for Archives., 2011. Accessed 8 of March 2025. Available: <https://cdn.nationalarchives.gov.uk/do>

- [cuments/information-management/digital-preservation-policies-guidance-draft-v4.2.pdf](#)
- [6] E. R. Preservation e A. Network, «Digital preservation policy tool», Information Society Technologies, 2003, Accessed: 5 of March 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.erpanet.org/guidance/docs/ERPANETPolicyTool.pdf>
- [7] D. Noonan, Digital preservation policy framework: «A case study», 2014, Accessed: 8 of March 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://kb.osu.edu/items/705da571-8e22-5557-a8a2-fea08890a5e2>
- [8] DELOS Network of Excellence, The DELOS Digital Library Reference Model Foundations for Digital Libraries, 2007. Accessed 1 March 2025. [Online]. Available: http://delosw.isti.cnr.it/files/pdf/ReferenceModel/DELOS_DLReferenceModel_096.pdf
- [9] Norwegian Ministry of Culture, National Strategy for Digital Preservation and Dissemination of Cultural Heritage, 2010. [Online]. Available: https://www.regjeringen.no/contentassets/f3f0e538cc704abda770db1ef2c5399b/en-gb/pdfs/stm200820090024000en_pdfs.pdf
- [10] National Library of Australia, Digital Preservation Policy, 2008 [Online]. Available: <https://catalogue.nla.gov.au/catalog/2513741>
- [11] Library and Archives Canada, Strategy for a digital preservation program, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://library-archives.canada.ca/eng/corporate/about-us/strategies-initiatives/Pages/strategy-digital-preservation-program.aspx>
- [12] M. Sheldon, Analysis of current digital preservation policies: archives, libraries, and museums», Junior Fellow with NDIPP, 2013., Accessed 1 of March 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://blogs.loc.gov/thesignal/2013/08/analysis-of-current-digital-preservation-policies-archives-libraries-and-museums/>
- [13] L. G. S. Souza e E. C. Aganette, «Política de preservação de documentos digitais: análise da estruturação e proposta de um procedimento operacional», Ciência da Informação, vol. 51, n.o 1, 2022
- [14] INTERPARES, Digital records pathways: topics in digital preservation: module 2: developing policy and procedures for digital preservation Vancouver: University of British Columbia, 2012. [Online]. Available: http://interpares.org/ip3/display_file.cfm?doc=ip3_canada_gs12_module_2_july-2012_DRAFT.pdf
- [15] N. Beagrie, N. Semple, P. Williams, e R. Wright, «Digital Preservation Policies Study Part 1: Final Report», Higher Education Funding Council for England, available at: www.jisc.ac.uk/media/documents/programmes/preservation/jisc_policy_p1finalreport.pdf, 2008.
- [16] N. MCGOVERN, Digital preservation policy framework: development guideline version 2.1. Ottawa: Canadian Heritage Information Network, 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://www.canada.ca/en/heritage-information-network/services/digital-preservation/policy-framework-development-guideline.html>
- [17] DIGITAL PRESERVATION COALITION, Digital preservation handbook. 2. ed. Glasgow: Digital Preservation Coalition, 2015. [Online]. Available: <https://www.dpconline.org/events/handbook>.
- [18] A. P. de HOLANDA e C. LACOMBE, «Recomendações para elaboração de política de preservação digital», Rio de Janeiro: Arquivo Nacional, 2019.
- [19] APARSEN, Exemplar good governance structures and data policies, 2014, Accessed 9 March 2025 [Online]. Available: http://www.alliancepermanentaccess.org/wpcontent/uploads/sites/7/downloads/2014/06/APARSEN-REP-D35_1-01-1_0_incURN.pdf
- [20] Ministerio de Cultura, Recursos profesionales. [Online]. Accessed 1 March 2025. Available: <https://www.cultura.gob.es/cultura/archivos/recursos-profesionales.html>
- [21] A. García González, S. Asensio Merino, Código de Derecho Cultural. Boletín Oficial del Estado. Ministerio de Cultura y Deporte. Madrid, 2024
- [22] A. López Sánchez, Código de Archivos y Patrimonio Documental. Boletín Oficial del Estado. Ministerio de Cultura y Deporte. Subdirección General de los Archivos Estatales. Madrid. 2025
- [23] Subdirección General de los Archivos Estatales, El archivo único. Modelo de referencia para la Administración General del Estado com proyección interadministrativa. Madrid, 2025
- [24] Law 11/2007, de 22 de junio, BOE, nº150. De acceso electrónico de los ciudadanos a los Servicios Públicos.
- [25] Royal Decree 1708/2011, de 18 de noviembre, BOE, nº284. Por el que se establece el Sistema Español de Archivos y se regula el Sistema de Archivos de la Administración General del Estado y de sus Organismos Públicos y su régimen de acceso
- [26] Royal Decree 1517/2009, de 2 de octubre. BOE, nº266. Patronato del Archivo General de Simancas
- [27] Law 6/2022, de 5 de agosto, BOE, nº226. De archivos y gestión documental de las Illes Balears
- [28] Royal Decree 203/2021, de 30 de marzo. BOE, nº77. Por el que se aprueba el Reglamento de actuación y funcionamiento del sector público por medios electrónicos.
- [29] Law 40/2015, de 1 de octubre, BOE, nº236. Régimen Jurídico del Sector Público
- [30] Law 39/2015, de 1 de octubre, BOE, nº236. Del Procedimiento Administrativo Común de las Administraciones Públicas
- [31] Royal Decree 4/2010, de 8 de enero, BOE, nº25. por el que se regula el Esquema Nacional de Interoperabilidad en el ámbito de la Administración Electrónica
- [32] ISO, ISO 14721:2012 Space data and information transfer systems – Open archival information system (OAIS) - Reference model. Geneva: International Standard Organization, 2012

- [33] Resolution of the Council of Ministers n.º 207/2024, DR, S.I nº252. Aprova a Estratégia Digital Nacional e o respetivo modelo de governação
- [34] Decree law n.º 447/88, de 10 de dezembro, DR, S.I nº 284. Diário da República: I série, n.º 284, Regula a pré-arquivagem de documentação
- [35] Decree law n.º 16/93, de 23 de janeiro, DR, S.I-A nº19, Estabelece o regime geral dos arquivos e do património arquivístico
- [36] C. Casaca, P. Penteado, Políticas de preservação digital em Portugal. Encontro Novos caminhos para a Preservação e o Acesso à Informação. Lisboa,2024. Accessed:8March2025.[Online].Available:<http://hdl.handle.net/10400.26/52883>
- [37] P. Penteado,Desenhando novas políticas para valorizar e preservar a informação digital: propostas da DGLAB para um Regime Jurídico. Encontro Nacional sobre Preservação Digital. Lisboa, 2022. Accessed: 8 March2025.[Online].Available:<https://www.keep.pt/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/01-Legislacao-Pedro-Penteado.pdf>

Author Biographies

Catarina Gasche is currently a PHD student in Information Science at the School of Arts and Humanities, University of Lisbon. She is a researcher with the Information Science Team at the Centre for Classical Studies (University of Lisbon). Her interests are archival science, digital preservation and combining politics with information science to understand the information landscape.

Luís Corujo serves as an Assistant Professor at the School of Arts and Humanities, University of Lisbon, where he directs the Information Science Master's program. He is a researcher with the Information Science Team at the Centre for Classical Studies (University of Lisbon) and a member of ISKO's Iberian Chapter.

